

NUTRIENT COMPOSITION AND USES OF BAMBARA GROUNDNUT (*VIGNIA SUBTERRANEA* (L.) VERDCOURT)

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ABSTRACT

Proximate and amino acid compositions of raw and roasted bambara groundnut seeds were determined. The dry matter values ranged from 95.24 - 96.36%; crude protein 20.05 - 22.54%; crude fat 7.15 - 8.31% and ash 3.40 - 3.48% for the raw and roasted seeds respectively. The crude fibre had values ranging from 4.88 to 5.48% and nitrogen free extract values ranged from 57.15 to 59.16% for the roasted and raw seeds respectively. Results on the amino acid profiles of raw and roasted bambara groundnut seeds showed that the concentrations of some amino acids like histidine, aspartic acid, proline, cystine, valine, methionine, isoleucine, tyrosine, and phenylalanine decreased due to heat processing. However, some amino acids like lysine, threonine, serine, glutamic acid, glycine, alanine and leucine had their concentrations increased with heat processing. The amino acid with the highest concentration in bambara groundnut was glutamic acid with 15.76g/16gN in the raw seeds and 15.91g/16gN in the roasted seeds. Sulphur-containing amino acids were found to be the most limiting. The concentrations of methionine were 1.04g/16gN and 0.97g/16gN while the concentrations of cystine were 1.25g/16gN and 0.71g/16gN for the raw and roasted seeds respectively. The essential amino acid, leucine had the highest value of 7.76g/16gN for the raw seeds and 7.99g/16gN for the roasted seeds of bambara groundnut. Bambara groundnut is used in several ways, which includes soup making, porridge, seeds grilled as snacks, in cake and bread, preparation of milk, fortification of baby food, seeds canned in gravy, in the preparation of various fried, or steamed products, such as “akara” (bean cake) and “moin-moin” and “okpa” (beans pudding) and as livestock feedstuff.

KEYWORDS: Nutrient, composition, uses, bambara groundnut

INTRODUCTION

Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranea* (L.) Verdc.) is one of the indigenous African crops currently receiving interest from researchers because of its high yield and resistance to diseases (Hepper, 1970) as well as its adaptability to poor soils and rain fall (Gwekwerere, 1995). Bambara groundnut has been cultivated in the tropical regions of Sub-Saharan Africa and Madagascar for many centuries, (Linnemann and Azam-Ali, 1993). Bambara groundnut was found by Dalziel in its genuinely wild state in 1901, in the North Yola province of Nigeria (Goli, 1995). Ledermann also found the wild plant the same year, near Garoua in northern Cameroon (Goli, 1995). Dalziel's finding was confirmed by Hepper in 1957. The distribution of wild bambara groundnut is now known to extend from Jos Plateau and Yola in Nigeria to Garoua in Cameroon and probably beyond.

Bambara groundnut as reported by Olomu (1995) contains crude protein 20.60%, it is high in lysine with fair amount of total sulphur amino acids. The seed is deficient in tryptophan, the bulk of the fat is unsaturated (about 59%) while 41% is saturated, proximate and mineral composition of raw, cooked, autoclaved and roasted bambara groundnut seeds were determined by Omoikhoje and Arijenwa (2004). Crude protein ranged from 18.92 - 21.67%, ether extract 6.45 - 7.47%, crude fibre 3.52 - 4.45, ash 2.75 - 4.56%, moisture content 6.80 - 11.20% and nitrogen free extract 45.93 - 59.04%. Results on the mineral composition indicated that calcium ranged from 2.64 - 2.81%, phosphorus 0.06 - 0.08%, potassium 0.79 - 0.82%, sodium 0.004 - 0.005%, magnesium 0.65 - 0.68%, iron 151 - 160 ppm and copper 2.4 - 2.6 mg/kg DM. Bambara groundnut seeds have been reported by Temple and Aliyu (1994) to contain 16 - 24% crude protein and about 6% ether extract with high proportions of lysine (6.6%) and methionine (1.3%). Leucine has been stated to be the most concentrated essential amino acid found in bambara groundnut (Olomu, 1995; Aremu *et al.*, 2006). Bambara groundnut is a well balanced food with a calorific value comparable with that of a high quality cereal grain (Barimila *et al.*, 1994).

Uses of bambara groundnut :

Bambara groundnut is mainly used for human consumption. The seeds are consumed either when immature or fully ripe and dry (Swanevelder, 1998). They can be eaten fresh, or grilled while still immature. At maturity, they become very hard, and therefore required cooking before any specific preparation (Goli, 1995). In many West African countries, the fresh pod are boiled with salt and pepper and eaten as a snack. In Cote d'Ivoire, the seed is used to make flour, which makes it more digestible (Goli, 1995). In East Africa, the beans are roasted, then pulverized, and used to make a soup, with or without condiments. Bread made from bambara groundnut flour has been reported in Zambia (Linnemann, 1990). Ripe dry seeds are either pounded to flour and boiled to a stiff porridge, or soaked and then boiled. The porridge keeps well and is traditionally used on journeys (Swanevelder, 1998). Zengeni and Mupamba (1995) reported that ripe dry seeds of bambara groundnut are roasted, broken into pieces, boiled, crushed and eaten as a relish with "sadza" (maize meal porridge). In restaurants in Angola and Mozambique, boiled salted seeds are often served as appetizers. Commercial canning of bambara groundnut in gravy is a successful industry in Ghana (Swanevelder, 1998), the product was thus available throughout the year and over 40,000 cans of various sizes were produced annually (Doku and Karikari, 1971; Begemann, 1986). In Nigeria the common use of bambara groundnut is to make a paste out of the dried seeds, which is then used in the preparation of various fried, or steamed products, such as "akara" (bean cake) and "moin-moin" and "okpa" (beans pudding) (Obizoba, 1983). Bambara groundnut can also be used in the fortification of cereal foods to improve the nutrient content for both baby and adult foods such as in the preparation of pap and pottage (Fabiya, E.F. personal communication). According to Karikari (1971), some tribes in Congo roasted the seeds of bambara groundnut and pounded them for oil extraction, despite the relatively low oil content of the seed.

Brough *et al.* (1993) reported that a trial of bambara groundnut milk was carried out which compared its flavour and composition with those of milks prepared from cowpea, pigeon pea and soybean. Bambara groundnut was ranked first, and while all milks were found to be acceptable, the lighter colour of the bambara groundnut was preferred. Bambara groundnut has long been used as an animal feed. Several workers have successfully fed processed bambara groundnut to livestock animals such as poultry (Oluyemi *et al.*, 1976; Onwudike and Eguakun, 1994; Arijeniwa and Omoikhoje, 2004) and rabbits (Joseph *et al.*, 2000; Akande, 2009). The haulms were found to be palatable (Doku and Karikari, 1971), and the leaves were reported to be rich in nitrogen and phosphorus and therefore suitable for livestock grazing (Rassel, 1960).

The objective of the study was to find out the usage of bambara groundnut and to determine its proximate and amino acid compositions in order to evaluate its nutritional potentials.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Processing of bambara groundnut seeds :

The bambara groundnut used in this study was obtained in the year 2005 from Bauchi main market, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The bambara groundnut seeds were sand-roasted. This involved the use of clean fine alluvial sand in a wide aluminum frying pan and heating the sand to the temperature of about 80°C. Sufficient quantity of each batch of the raw seeds to cover about two-third of the area of sand was placed on the sand. The seeds and sand were mixed together by constant stirring to prevent the burning of the seed coat and enhance even distribution of heat. The sand roasting of bambara groundnut took 7 - 9 minutes. The sand was then sieved from the seeds and allowed to cool and then milled in hammer mill.

Proximate analysis :

Proximate analysis of bambara groundnut (both raw and processed seeds) were carried out using the methods outlined by the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC, 1990). The proximate compositions of the bambara groundnut seeds are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Proximate composition (%) of raw and roasted bambara groundnut seeds

Content	Raw seed	Roasted seed
Dry matter	95.24	96.36
Crude protein	20.05	22.54
Crude fat	7.15	8.31
Crude fibre	5.48	4.88
Ash	3.40	3.48
Nitrogen free extract	59.16	57.15

Amino acid analysis :

The amino acid compositions of the samples were determined using the method described by Spackman *et al.* (1958). The samples were dried to constant weight and defatted. A known weight of the defatted sample was hydrolysed under vacuum with 7ml of 6N HCl in a sealed pyrex tube at 105°C. Immediately after cooling, it was filtered through non-absorbent cotton wool. The filtrate was dried at 40°C using rotary evaporator.

The amino acids in the flask were diluted with 5ml of acetate buffer (pH 2.0) and 5 to 10 microlitre was loaded into the cartridge of Technicon Sequential Multisample amino acid analyzer (TSM). The steam carrying the amino acid reagent mixture went through a heating bath where development of the coloured reaction product occurred. The absorbance was proportional to the concentration of each amino acid and was measured by colorimeter.

Table 2 : Amino acid profiles of raw and roasted bambara groundnut seeds (g/16gN)

Amino acids	Raw bambara	Roasted bambara
Lysine	5.93	6.22
Histidine	2.95	1.87
Arginine	6.41	6.41
Aspartic acid	12.95	11.72
Threonine	3.11	3.62
Serine	4.46	4.69
Glutamic acid	15.76	15.91
Proline	3.60	3.30
Glycine	3.01	3.36
Alanine	3.52	4.80
Cystine	1.25	0.71
Valine	4.51	3.96
Methionine	1.04	0.97
Isoleucine	4.56	3.95
Leucine	7.76	7.99
Tyrosine	3.19	2.88
Phenylalanine	5.43	4.12
Tryptophan	ND	ND

ND = Not determined

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proximate compositions of the bambara groundnut seeds are presented in Table 1. The dry matter values ranged from 95.24 - 96.36%; crude protein 20.05 - 22.54%; crude fat 7.15 - 8.31% and ash 3.40 - 3.48% for the raw and roasted seeds respectively. The crude fibre had values ranging from 4.88 to 5.48% and nitrogen free extract values ranged from 57.15 to 59.16% for the roasted and raw seeds respectively. The range of values obtained in this study for crude protein, crude fat and ash are close to those reported by Onwudike and Eguakun (1994), for crude protein (20.60 - 20.90%); crude fat (7.35 - 7.48%) and ash (2.76 - 3.78%).

The amino acid profiles of raw and roasted bambara groundnut seeds are shown in Table 2. The results revealed that for bambara groundnut, the concentrations of some amino acids like histidine, aspartic acid, proline, cystine, valine, methionine, isoleucine, tyrosine, and phenylalanine decreased due to heat processing. However, some amino acids like lysine, threonine, serine, glutamic acid, glycine, alanine and leucine had their concentrations increased with heat processing. In this study, it was observed that the amino acid with the highest concentration in bambara groundnut was glutamic acid and was followed by aspartic acid. Similar observations had been previously reported by some authors (Doku *et al.*, 1978; Olaofe and Akintayo, 2000; Aremu *et al.*, 2006). Glutamic acid for the raw bambara groundnut seeds was 15.76g/16gN and 15.91g/16gN for the roasted seeds. The values obtained for aspartic acid were 12.95g/16gN and 11.72g/16gN for the raw and roasted seeds respectively. These values are comparable to those reported by Doku *et al.* (1978) and Aremu *et al.* (2006). Onwudike and Eguakun (1994) however obtained higher values for glutamic acid in bambara groundnut than those reported in this study. These authors reported 28.83g/16gN and 30.60g/16gN for the raw and for heat-treated bambara respectively. The essential amino acid leucine had the highest value of 7.76g/16gN for the raw seeds and 7.99g/16gN for the roasted seeds of bambara groundnut this agrees with the findings of Olomu (1995) and Aremu *et al.* (2006), these researchers reported that leucine was the most concentrated

essential amino acid in bambara groundnut. The values obtained for leucine was closely followed by arginine with the value of 6.41g/16gN for both raw and roasted seeds. The lysine values of 5.93g/16gN for raw bambara groundnut and 6.22g/16gN for the roasted seeds obtained in this study are within the range of 6.63 to 6.97g/16gN reported by Doku *et al.* (1978). Sulphur-containing amino acids were found to be the most limiting. Methionine values were 1.04g/16gN and 0.97g/16gN while cystine had values of 1.25g/16gN and 0.71g/16gN for the raw and roasted seeds respectively. These values were also close to those reported by Doku *et al.* (1978) but much lower than those reported by Onwudike and Eguakun (1994). Variations in the amino acid concentrations between this study and those reported by other authors might be due to some factors like; the effect of geographical location which has been reported to have significant influence on the composition of amino acids in plant protein (Oshodi, 1993; Bhatti *et al.*, 2000). Other factors include; differences in cultivar, effect of processing method on seed and acid digestion method used in preparing the samples for amino acid analysis (Wathelet, 1999; Hassan and Umar, 2005).

CONCLUSION

The results obtained in this study revealed the nutritional potentials of bambara groundnut seed for livestock feeding. This unconventional protein source could replace part of maize and soybean in the diet of livestock animals. Further research should be geared towards evaluating the effect of processing methods other than roasting on the nutritional qualities of bambara groundnut.

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